

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GENDER AND STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

Akeem AMEEN¹, Saheed Olalekan YAHYA², Nusirat YUSUF³ and Mohammed Mustapha SAIDU⁴

^{1,2,3}Kwara State College of Education (Technical) Lafiagi

⁴Bauchi State College of Education

Abstract

Gender is an important language learning variable. The purpose of this study was thus to examine the influence of gender on the formation of language learning attitudes among college students. Hence, the study made use of Mixed Methods Research (MMR). In specific, the design was an explanatory sequential mixed method involving formulation of questions, data collection, data analysis, interpretation, and validation. The respondents of this study were the students of Kwara State College of Education (Technical) Lafiagi, a technical-based college situated in Edu Local Government Area of Kwara State of Nigeria. A sample of 265 students were taken for the administration of the questionnaire. In the same vein, the study collected a sample of 27 students for the interview protocol session being approximately 10% of the sample population used for the quantitative phase of data collection. The study made use of an adopted questionnaire; Attitude towards Language (ATol) scale as used by Eshghinejad (2016) based on Baker's (1992) LLA Model. It was found, among others that there was no significant difference in the attitudes of both male and female students towards learning of English language since the p-value (=0.641) was greater than 0.05. That is, the students' attitudes towards learning English were same and positive. Hence, in the context of this study, gender had no overtly observed influence on the college students' attitudes towards English language. In other words, attitude appeared to be gender-general rather than being gender-specific. Therefore, both the male and female students had the same attitudes towards learning English. Also, the study revealed that as gender did not have any significant influence on the overall attitude, there was no significant difference in the attitudes of both male and female college students at the level of each of the components of language learning attitudes. Based on this, it can be argued that while attitudes are important learning variable in language learning, gender had effect on the attitude formation.

Introduction

English language learning, throughout the world, is an object of important desire and attention. It is considered a great necessity while an ability to communicate in it is taken as a prime objective of many people for several reasons. This is not unconnected to the fact that English is an international or global language (Crystal, 2003). There is thus a burning desire among people of different climes to learn English language being such a language with fame, prestige, and popularity, because as Reyes (2018) put it, learning English language has become a great need since it is a world language. However, learning a second language is a process that is influenced by several elements. One of such is the individual language learner's attitude. Attitude is such an

important concept in learning process, and it is used to refer to the totality of feelings, emotion, acts, etc. that a language learner has or displays towards a particular language or language learning in general based on knowledge and belief about the object (Ajzen, 2005).

Learners' attitudes are thus very important in language learning. They are the dimensions that could influence English learning process (Octavia, 2017). The general belief is that if learners have or develop positive attitudes towards a language, it can facilitate language learning and relate to the success in the second language acquisition. Supporting this view, Borja (2016) had earlier argued that one of the most pressing concerns in education today is students' attitudes toward learning. Learning English could be made successful if

the teachers correctly identify the learners' attitudes. They will assist in the development of a good attitude in the students, which will help to counterbalance their negative attitude. Hence, attitude exerts a direct influence upon language learner's response to situation (Bartram, 2010) thereby making it an important variable in language learning. It determines how a language learner reacts to the subject and how he performs. Attitudes are thus considered major components in the process of motivating learners. In consonance with this, Dashti and Aldashti (2015) argued that students' ability to learn a language can be influenced by the attitudes towards the target language. If they believe the English language, for example, has something to do with them as individuals or plays a significant role in their future aspirations, their attitudes will be greatly changed.

The crucial role played by attitude has thus been examined and established in various research and studies with focus on the role of attitudes in first language, second language, modern foreign language, and bilingual teaching and learning situations (Beamont & O'Brien, 2000). This thus provide an important social research route to access indications of current community thoughts and beliefs as well as preference and desires. This has been based on the conviction that there is connection between attitudes and behaviour as well as relationship between attitude and language performance. Also stressing the ESL learners' attitudes, Hussein El-Omari (2016) observed that learning English has always been a great challenge that many learners of second language encounter. Displaying poor attitudes, some of the learners would skip school and classes due to their low English performance. In some cases, they (the students) obstruct the teaching-learning process in the classrooms which usually end in hating the English language teachers and even the whole school. Also, in relation to attitudes, Octavia (2017) held that factors such as attitude, motivation, aptitude, intelligence, and age are the dimensions that could influence learning process with the general belief is that if learners have or develop. The positive attitudes towards a language, it can facilitate language learning

and relate to the success in the second language acquisition. In consonance with this, Borja (2016) argued that one of the most pressing concerns in education today is students' attitudes toward learning. Learning English could be made successful if the teachers correctly identify the learners' attitudes. They will help to construct a positive feeling that can counteract the negative disposition in the students.

That is perhaps why Dashti and Aldashti (2015) therefore held that students' ability to learn a language can be influenced by the attitudes towards the target language. If, for instance, they feel English language has something to do with them as individuals or plays important role in their plans, their attitudes will be immensely influenced. To that end, attitude, a mental state of readiness that exerts a directive influence upon one's response to situation (Bartram, 2010), is an important variable in language learning. It determines how a learner reacts to the subject and how he performs. The crucial role played by attitude has been examined and established in various research and studies. For instance, Makrami (2010) carried out a study of effects of attitude on Saudi university undergraduate learners of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in relation to a sample of some other category of students learning English for General Purposes (EGP). It was found out, among others, that learners' success in English, weighed by their scores on the final English test, correlated more with their attitude, motivation, and anxiety more than the ESP group. In addition, Chalak and Kassaian (2010) investigated the motivational orientation and attitudes of 108 English translation major students at Islamic Azad University, Iran. They found out that the learners tended to learn English for both instrumental and integrative reasons and their attitude towards the target language was generally highly positive in nature. Here again, it could be seen that this study by Chalak and Kassaian (2010) employed Gardner's (1985) model of language learning attitudes.

In the same vein, gender plays an equally important role in language learning. For instance, as reported by Aslan (2009), gender

influences learning strategies adopted by either gender. This suggests that different language acquisition strategies are used by males and females. That is why, according to Gascoigne (2002), males are more likely to use interruptions, instructions, and sentence-initial conjunctions, whereas females are more likely to employ intensifiers, questions, personal pronouns, word-initial adverbs, and justifiers (Gascoigne, 2002). Besides, there is widespread belief that females tend to be better L2 learners than males. That is, according to some studies in second language learning, females are said to have advantages as they appear to be more successful. As an illustration, females seem to outperform male on a listening comprehension test. Furthermore, girls are more likely than boys to begin speaking earlier, use longer sentences, and have more favourable attitudes toward reading and higher reading achievement. It must be noted however, according to Saville-Troike (2006), that this belief is probably primarily a social construct, based on outcomes which reflect cultural and socio-psychological constraints and influences.

Gender is often believed to play a significant role in pupils' English language ability. In this sense, some academics believe that female students outperform male students in language classes. According to Chukuma (2004), gender, for example, is a determining factor for an individual's degree of performance and competency in particular areas. He thus believed that a student's gender has a significant impact on his academic achievement. Males and females are often thought to have differing talents when it comes to language learning. Gardner and Lambert (2013), for instance, found that females had a more positive attitude toward English language learning and were more driven to learn a second language than male counterparts in their study of males and females' attitudes toward English language learning while a study conducted by Alnatheer (2013) showed that males displayed a high level of self-reported communicative competence. However, it's worth noting that this could be linked to Saudi men's proclivity to communicate and express themselves more than Saudi women. This is especially evident when we consider that many Saudi ladies are

hesitant and unwilling to communicate, particularly with men. In this case, one of the factors that can be attributed to this is the cultural aspect as outside of the classroom, and even at home, they are not receptive to speaking. In contrast, a research of students' affective attitudes toward English class at Gazi Educational Faculty found that female students had higher favourable attitudes toward English than male students. Nevertheless, in many circumstances, women and men tend to use language differently (Maghsudi, Sharifi & Abedi, 2015). This is still open to continuous debates.

Hence, several studies have linked students' attitudes to language learning as a predictor of their performance and proficiency in English language. This establishes the importance of learners' attitudes in English classrooms. It is believed that this study will provide an insight into

the attitudes of college students towards learning English language, and the influence of gender on attitude formation. The study is thus interested in examining the influence of gender on students' attitudes towards English language.

Methodology

The study made use of mixed methods research (MMR). In specific, the design was an explanatory sequential mixed method involving formulation of questions, data collection, data analysis, interpretation, and validation (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). What this means is that the study involved the use of both open-ended (interviews) and close-ended (questionnaire) data collection instruments to obtain the needed information. It thus had to do with statistical data analysis and content analysis/triangulation. Therefore, considering the population of the students, a sample of 265 students were taken for the administration of the questionnaire. This, according to Krejcie and Morgan (1970), and Creswell (2012), was considered the acceptable minimum size needed to estimate the true population proportion as it would lead to 95% confidence level at 5% margin error. In the same vein, the

study collected a sample of 27 students for the interview protocol session being approximately the 10% of the sample population used for the quantitative phase of data collection. The study made use of an adopted questionnaire; Attitude towards Language (AToL) scale as used by Eshghinejad (2016) based on Baker's (1992) LLA Model. The instrument contained 10 items for each of the attitudinal components; cognitive, affective, and conative, and it was based on a five-point Likert scale level of "Strongly Disagree (1)" to "Strong Agree (5)".

Results And Finding

Gender is an important factor in language learning (Stewart & McDermott, 2004) and the study of personality as well as attitude is relevant to investigate individual difference across gender. To that end, this study attempted to investigate the role of gender in students' formation of the attitude towards English language. The question was answered through the data collected from the questionnaire and were analysed using t-test. The findings were also corroborated by the results from interview. It was to investigate

whether the students would differ in their attitudes towards learning English language based on their gender. Based on the analysis, however, it showed that there was no significant difference in the attitudes of both male and female students towards learning of English language since the p-value (=0.641) is greater than

0.05. That is, the students' attitudes towards learning English were same and positive. Hence, in the context of this study, gender had no overtly observed influence on the college students' attitudes towards English language. In other words, attitude appeared to be gender-general rather than being gender-specific. Therefore, both the male and female students had the same attitudes towards learning English. Also, it revealed that as gender did not have any significant influence on the overall attitude, there was no significant difference in the attitudes of both male and female college students at the level of each of the components of language learning attitudes. The Table below therefore shows the result of the t-test analysis of the influence of gender on the students' attitudes towards learning English language.

T-test Analysis of gender influence on students' Overall Attitude to Learning of English

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	Df	P	Decision
Male	121	248.43	24.52	0.466	263	0.641	Not Significant
Female	144	246.40	27.82				

As shown on the table, 121 male students participated in the study with a total number of 144 female students. However, as can be seen, the table shows that there was no significant difference in the attitude of male and female students towards learning of English language since the p-value (=0.641) is greater than the critical value of 0.05. That is, based on the results in this study, it was revealed that the students' attitudes towards learning English were same and positive. Hence, in the context of this study, gender had no overtly observed influence on the college students' attitudes towards English language. In other words, attitude appeared to be gender-general rather than being gender-specific. This means that there was no significant difference in the attitude of the students towards

learning English language based on gender. Therefore, both the male and female students had the same attitudes towards learning English were not dictated by gender. This could be that both had equal awareness about the relevance of English in their lives. It could as well be because is a compulsory subject that must be passed at all levels.

The finding in the present study that there is no significant difference in the attitudes of the students in college based on their gender disagrees with Eshghinejad (2016) who found gender differences in the general language learning attitudes among the students. He said there is a statistically significant difference between the attitudes of students based on

gender. That's, the attitudes of female EFL students towards English were higher than that of the male ones. Similarly, the finding is not in line with the report of Ma (2014) who in the study of gender differences in the undergraduates' attitudes towards EFL in Tianjin found that girls had more positive attitude to EFL than boys. In addition, this finding that attitude was not gender specific is in contrary to Garner and Lambert (2013) who observed that female learners had more positive attitude towards the second language and that they were motivated towards learning a second language than their male counterparts. It is also in contrary to Shakouri and Saligheh (2012) who concluded that male language learners showed more positive attitudes in language tasks than their female counterparts. Moreover, Mtawaa (2017) examined the impact of gender on students' attitude towards English in Saudi Arabia. Finding revealed an overall positive attitude towards English among the students. However, it revealed attitudinal differences among the students with males showing more positive attitude towards English than their female counterparts.

Also, the finding is also dissimilar to the finding of Oluwatelure (2015) when gender difference in an attitude of students towards science in secondary schools was investigated. Results showed that there was significance gender difference in the attitude of male and female students. He thus concluded that a gender sensitive approach must be employed to bridge up the gap in the attitudes of public secondary schools' students. Also reporting a contrary finding, Imasuen and Omorogbe (2016) in their study of the influence of gender on students' attitude towards mathematics found that although the students had positive attitude towards mathematics, there was a difference in the attitudes of male and female students with a t-value of -0.498 and p-value of 0.655 and 148 degrees of freedom. More so, Chiesi and Primi (2016) reported that females showed more negative attitudes when compared to males. In the same vein, this finding also contradicts the finding of Abidin, Pour-Mohammadi & Alzwari (2012) in the study of Libyan Secondary School students' attitudes towards learning English language in terms of conative, cognitive, and

affective aspects. His study revealed there were statistically significant attitudinal differences in terms of gender with female students having slightly higher positive attitude than their male counterpart in secondary school in Libya. Similarly, Gomleksiz (2010) reported statistically difference in the attitude of students towards English Language learning in terms of gender. The result reveals that female students had more positive attitudes than male students did. The finding is, therefore, in contrary to the finding of the present study where no significant difference was observed in the overall study attitude to English.

Besides, the attitudes of students the study of English and French were investigated by Soku, Simpeh and Osafo-Adu (2011) in Ghana. Results indicated that gender had a significant effect on the students' attitudes to English with female showing a better attitude to English than their Male counterparts ($M=24.87$, $SD = 3.60$; $M=23.696$, $SD=3.00$) This finding, therefore, contradicts the finding of the present study where no significant difference was recorded. Also, in their study of the gender differences in people's attitude towards COVID-19 in selected eight countries, Galasso, Pons, Profeta, Becher and Brouard (2020) found that there were gender differences in attitude with women likely to see the disease as a very serious health problem. Although the study was not related to learning, it had to do with attitude in terms of beliefs and behaviours. In another study, Wayar (2017) also reported significant attitudinal differences among the students in Northern Nigeria in term of gender. The study's results showed that female learners developed more positive attitude towards English Language than their male counterparts. Hence, there are significant differences between male and female students in their attitudinal orientation. This is not in line with the finding of the present study even though both studies were set in Nigeria. Contributing, Appiah-Kubi (2019) reported an overall high positive attitude towards English language learning among the students in Kumasi. It was however, shown that there was a correlation between gender and attitudes towards the target language, target community and overall attitude of the students. This implies that even though the finding is in

line with the present study in terms of the positive attitude among the student, they differ as regards the role of gender on the students. While the present study found no significant difference in their attitudes based on gender, Appiah-kubi (2019) did.

However, the finding is in tandem with the findings of Leome (2006) in Wayar (2017) when it was argued that it is pointless to speak of superiority of gender as there is little justification for separate analyses of males and females. This was also supported by Fakeye (2010) in his study that there was no statistically significant difference in the attitudes of male and female learners. It needs to be pointed out, therefore, that gender is likely to interact with other factors and so, it will not always be the case that a particular gender does better than the other or displays a particular type of attitude while the other does not. In summary, their attitude was not gender specific. This means that both can have positive attitude towards learning English (as we had in this case) or vice versa as some other factor could come into play. Anasi (2018) conducted a study of the influence of gender on attitude towards the use of social media for continuing professional development among academic librarians. It was found out that there is no statistically significant gender difference in their attitude ($t = 0.097$, $df = 54$ and $P > 0.05$). This thus confirms the finding in the present study where gender had no statistically significant influence on the students' language learning attitudes. Oba and Lawrence (2014) examined the effects of gender on students' attitudes to physics. They reported that gender that gender had no effect on the students' attitude. Their study revealed that $F(1.151) = 34.161$ and $F_1 = 3064.154$ at df of 1 and $p > 0.005$ level of significant. Hence, $F(1.151) = 0.694$ is not significant statistically. In addition, this finding thus agrees with the findings of Naqeeb (2014) when the attitude of Law students at the Arab American University, Jenin, towards learning English was investigated. It was found out that the students had positive attitudes towards learning English and that gender had no impact or influence on their attitudes.

In the same view, Akram, and Ghani (2013) investigated the role of gender in attitudes towards learning English among twelfth-grade

Pakistani students who had studied English for 11 years. The results regarding the gender differences in their motivation to learn English showed that there are no statistically significant differences between males and females in their attitudes and motivation to learn English language. This finding by Akram and Ghani (2013), therefore, upholds the finding in the present study where no significant gender difference was found in the attitudes towards learning English language in the college. This implies that the subjects in both studies shared the same perceptions about learning English language and showed the same positive attitudes regardless of their gender. This finding is also like the report of Alzaidiyeen (2017) in his study of the English as foreign language students' attitudes towards the use of ipad in language learning. While the results revealed that most of the students had positive attitudes for the use of Ipad, there was no statistically meaningful difference in their attitude based on gender with $t(107) = 0.257$ at $P = 0.798$. In a study of the relationship between gender and students' attitudes towards using mathematical software, Ocak (2006) reported that gender had no relation to students' attitudes thereby confirming the finding of the present finding. In sum, therefore, as findings in the earlier research showed inconsistency, the findings in this study showed that gender has no significant effect on the students' language learning attitudes. That is, language learning attitude is not gender based. In other words, therefore, there is no significant difference in the attitudes of students learning English according to gender.

To further provide insight on the perceived role of gender on the students' attitudes towards learning English language, interview data were collected. When asked whether they thought their gender affects their attitudes to English, majority of them believed that gender had no effect on their language learning attitudes. Excerpts from their responses are presented below.

Student 1: Well, I'm a male, and for me, my gender has nothing to do with my attitude towards learning the English language.

Student 2: No, it doesn't but it depends on the individual.

Student 3: Personally no

Student 4: No

Student 5: I don't believe in such. I believe in ambition irrespective of the gender.

Student 6: I don't think so.

Student 7: It actually doesn't. Anyone can learn any language and be good at it. All one needs is to be exposed to the right/suitable environment.

Student 8: I don't think it does. It all depends on personal mindset not gender. It shouldn't be gender that influences our attitude towards learning English language.

Student 10: I don't think so.

Student 12: No.

Student 15: No, I don't think it does. Gender doesn't influence learning.

From the interview data therefore, the respondents held that their gender had no effect on their attitudes. Even though few of the respondents believed that gender influenced their attitudes towards learning English language as we have in the excerpt below, the overwhelming results showed that attitude is not gender specific.

Student 9: *I believe that ladies usually show positive attitude towards learning of English language. Most especially here to show their proficiency and competency in English language that's why many use hyper correction, omission among others. Most importantly in English there are situations where we consider expression a manly one or otherwise. Besides, English is a sexist language itself.*

According to most of the responses, therefore, the students held that gender does not determine their attitudes towards learning the English language. They believed that it all depends on the individual concerned as well as ambition and personal mindset. In sum, the results from the interview confirmed the finding from the quantitative analysis that there is no difference in the students' attitudes based on

gender. This is in line with the result of Reddy (2017) who found no significant difference in the overall attitudes of the students based on gender. It is also in agreement with that of Shams (2008) in Eshghinejad (2016) who was reported to have also carried out a study of student's attitudes towards learning English language and found that the students had general positive attitudes towards English regardless of gender. However, Ma (2014) in the study of gender differences in the undergraduates' attitudes towards EFL in Tianjin found that girls had more positive attitude to EFL than boys. That, the finding in the current study as regards gender difference in the overall attitudes of the students differs from that of Ma's (2014) finding. Chiesi and Primi (2016) also reported that females showed more negative attitudes when compared to males.

Conclusion

The general purpose of this study was to investigate the college students' attitudes towards learning English and how attitudes related with their gender. It was found that there was no significant difference in the students' attitudes towards learning English language based on

gender. That is, the results showed no gender differential in the students' attitudes towards learning English language. In other words, therefore, regardless of their gender, the students' attitudes towards learning English were same and positive. Based on this therefore, this study concludes that attitude, and gender are important variables in language teaching and learning which must be given adequate consideration by the teachers of English. Hence, learning English can be successful if the teachers of English can correctly identify the language learners' attitudes so that they can construct a positive feeling that can counteract the negative feeling of the learners. This is because positive attitudes can affect the language learners' motivation and their success in language tasks. Teachers of English should identify learners' attitudes and personality traits as this will lead to successful language teaching and learning. This is because, as opined by various scholars, attitudes are factors which determine the worth and values placed on a target language by an individual learner.

Funding

(TETFund/DESS/COE/ILORIN/ARJ/1)
“TETFund Projects 2019-2021”

References

- Abidin, M., Mohammadi, M., & Alzwari, H. (2012). EFL students' attitudes toward learning English language: the case of Libyan secondary school students. *Asian Social Science*, 8 (2), 119-134.
- Ajzen, I. (2005). *Attitudes, personality, and behavior*. Berkshire, McGraw-Hill Education.
- Akram, M. & Ghani, M. (2013). Gender and language learning motivation. *Academic Research International*, 4(2): 536-540.
- Alnatheer, A. A. (2013). *The role of motivation and motivational strategies in Saudi students' communicative competence in English*. Thesis submitted to Faculty of Education Queensland University of Technology Brisbane, Queensland, Australia.
- Alzaidiyeen, N. J. (2017). English as a foreign language students' attitude toward the utilisation of iPad in language learning. *Malaysian Online Journal of Education Technology*, 5(3): 16-24.
- Anasi, S. N. (2018). Influence of gender on attitude towards the use of social media for continuing professional development among academic librarians in Nigeria. *Information and Learning Unit*, 119(3/4): 226-240.
- Appiah-Kubi, R. (2019). *The influence of gender on attitudes and motivation towards learning English as a second language: A case of Ghanaian senior secondary school students*. An unpublished MA thesis submitted to the University of Bergen.
- Aslan, O. (2009). *The role of gender and language learning strategies in learning English*. An unpublished MA thesis submitted to Middle East Technical University.
- Bartram, B. (2010). *Attitudes to modern foreign language learning*. London: Continuum.
- Beaumont, M. and O'Brien, T. (2000). *Collaborative Research in Second Language Education*. Stoke-on-Trent: Trentham.
- Borja, C. (2016). *Attitude in English and competence of students at integrated refinery petrochemical complex (IRPCT) Technological College, Rayong, Thailand*. An unpublished MA thesis submitted to the College of Open Distance Education and Transnational Education Ifugao State University Lamut, Ifugao, Philippines.
- Chalak, A., & Kassaian, Z. (2010). Motivation and attitudes of Iranian undergraduate EFL students towards learning English. *GEMA Online Journal of Language Studies*, 10, 37-56.
- Chiesi, F. & Primi, C. (2015). *Gender differences in attitudes toward statistics: Is there a case for a confidence gap?* A paper presented at CERME 9- Ninth Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education, Charles University in Prague, Faculty of Education; ERME, Feb 2015, Prague, Czech Republic, 622-628.
- Chukuma, O. (2004). *Language learning at university: Exploring the role of concepts and skills*. London: Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Boston: Pearson.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Fifth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a Global Language*.

- Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Dashti, F. & Aldashti, A. (2015). EFL College Students' Attitude towards Mobile Learning. *International Education Studies*, 8(8), 13-20.
- Eshghinejad, S. (2016). EFL students' attitudes toward learning English language: The case study of Kashan University Students. *Cogent education*, 3, 1-13.
- Fakeye, D. (2010). Students' personal variables as correlates of academic achievement in English as a second language in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 22(3), 205- 211.
- Galasso, V. Pons, P., Becher, M. Brouchard, S. & Foucault, M. (2020). Gender differences in COVID-19 attitudes and behavior: Panel evidence from eight countries. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 117(44).
- Gardner, R.C. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. London: Edward Arnold.
- Gardner, R. and Lambert, W. (2013). *Gardner and Lambert's theories of Language Learning Motivation*. Retrieved from <http://prezi.com/.../gardner-lamberts>.
- Gascoigne, C. (2002). The role of gender in L2 interaction: Socialization via L2 materials. *Encuentro Revista de Investigación e Innovación en la Clase de Idioma*, 13/14, 81- 89
- Given, L. M. (2008). *The sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Gomleksiz, M. N. (2010). An evaluation of students' attitudes toward English language learning in terms of several variables. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, (9), 913-915.
- Hussein El-Omari, A. (2016). Factors Affecting Students' Achievement in English Language Learning. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 6(2), 9-18.
- Imasuen, K. & Omorogbe, D. E. A. (2016). The influence of gender on junior secondary school students' attitudes towards mathematics in Ovia North East Local Government Area of Edo State. *African Research Review*, 10(4), 115-126.
- Krejcie, R. V. and Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Education and Psychology Measurement*.
- Ma, D. (2014). Gender Differences in the Undergraduates' Attitudes towards EFL. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 5, (6), 1348-1352.
- Maghsudi, M, Sharifi, E & Sharari, A. (2015). The effect of gender on Foreign Language Learning. *International Journal of Educational Investigation*, 2(2), 162-166.
- Makrami, B. H. (2010). *Motivation and attitude of Saudi University's Learners of English for specific purposes*. Dissertation submitted to the Department of Curriculum and Teaching and the Faculty of the Graduate School of Education of the University of Kansas.
- Mtawaa, J. (2017). Examining the impact of gender and students' parents on attitudes towards English: The case of Saudi Arabian students and their parents in Al-Kamal College of Science and Arts. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 7(4), 233-238.
- Naqeeb, H. (2014). Attitudes of law students at Arab-American University-Jenin towards learning English as a foreign language. *AAUJ Journal*, 6: 1-15.
- Ocak, M. A. (2006). The relationship between gender and students' attitudes and experience of using a mathematical software program (MATLAB). *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 7(2), 124-129.
- Octavia, H. (2017). *The Correlation between Personality Traits: Extraversion/Introversion and Students' Attitudes in Learning English as a Foreign Language*.
- Oluwatelure, T. A. (2015). Gender differences in achievement and attitudes of publicsecondary school students towards science. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6, 87-92.
- Reddy, L. (2017) Gender Differences in Attitudes to Learning Science in Grade 7, *African Journal of Research in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 21(1), 26-36.
- Reyes, V. T. (2018). *Psychological personality factors in learning English foreign language*. Bona, Dominican Republic.
- Saville-Troike, M. (2006). *Introducing second language acquisition*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Shakouri, N. & Saligheh, M.K. (2012). Revisiting Age and Gender Influence in Second Language Acquisition. *Advances in English Linguistics (AEL)*, 1 (1), 1-6.
- Stewart, A. & McDermott, C. (2004). Gender in Psychology. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 55, 519-544.